

The Ripple Effect of Remittances on Educational Attainment: Lessons from Liberia

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21st April 2024

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9,535 Words

Abstract

This study investigates the impact of remittances on educational attainment among Liberian households using the 2014-2015 Liberian Household Income and Expenditure Survey. Considering Liberia's challenging socioeconomic conditions, where remittances account for a significant portion of GDP, my research aims to highlight the role of remittance flows in influencing educational attainment. By employing Instrumental Variable (IV) probit models, my analysis determines a positive and significant relationship between remittances and school enrolment for individuals aged 6-24. The findings suggest that remittances relax household financial constraints, allowing for greater investment into education. Going further, the influence of different individual and household characteristics on attainment is discussed. My study contributes to the literature by focusing on a region that has been relatively underrepresented, offering important insights in the context of Sub-Saharan Africa. Finally, my results underscore the importance of considering remittances in policy implementations aimed at enhancing educational access and quality in Liberia.

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1. Introduction

Remittances play a vital role in catalysing growth in developing countries. For many households in low-income countries (LICs), remittances act as a necessary source of income to sustain consumption and relax budget constraints. This may in turn increase investment in the education of the household's children (Bansak & Chezum (2009)). Also, households which receive remittances may depend less on children's labour, which provides more time for schooling. Additionally, recent literature studying a 'positive brain drain' indicates that migration prospects and subsequent remittances can raise the expected return to human capital development, thus fostering household investment into education (Beine et al (2008)). Ultimately, if households actively funnel remittances into educational investments, we should expect to see greater educational attainment for remittance-receiving households. It is the objective of my research to investigate the relationship between remittances and educational attainment.

Much literature has been published analysing the relationship between remittances and educational attainment at a national level: Tajikistan (Köllner (2013)), El Salvador (Cox & Ureta (2003)), Jordan (Mansour et al (2011)) and more. However, there has been limited recent literature dedicated to the relationship in Africa. The significance of this research gap is highlighted by the fact that in 2022, 11 out of the 38 countries where remittances exceeded 8% of GDP were in Africa (The World Bank (2022)). The unique challenges and opportunities in Africa, combined with the high reliance on remittances for many of its countries, highlight the need for focused research in this area. Mohammed (2022) examines the relationship between remittances and human development in Sub-Saharan Africa using macro data from multiple countries. I will instead use micro data, focusing on analysing the influence of remittances on educational attainment in Liberia at the household level. At the time of the survey, international remittances accounted for 20.3% of Liberia's GDP (The World Bank (2022)), emphasising the appropriateness of using Liberia to study this relationship. This represented a flow of \$654.4 million into Liberia (The World Bank (2022)). Remittances sent to Liberia can be either formal or informal depending on the method of transfer (Kruah (2017)). Formal remittances define money sent through banking channels, other financial institutions, or money transfer operators like MoneyGram. Remittances are referred to as informal when the money transferred does not follow formal channels (Freund & Spatafora (2005)). This most commonly occurs with cash transfers between friends and relatives.

The choice of Liberia as a case study is appropriate not only because of its significant receipt of remittances but also because it is a representative of post-conflict countries where remittances might play an important role in recovery. Research will be conducted employing data from the 2014-2015 Liberian Household Income and Expenditure Survey. If a significant link is determined by my analysis, then there will be important policy implications for the Liberian government to best utilise this relationship.

2. Literature Review

The relationship between remittances and educational attainment has been widely researched in the existing literature. The previous research conducted has not reached a unanimous verdict. There exists literature that determines that there is a significant positive relationship, that there is no real relationship, and that there even exists a negative relationship. The majority of the existing papers fall into the first camp, finding that receiving remittances positively influences education attainment. One of the most influential and pioneering papers on

this topic is by Hanson & Woodruff (2003), who focus on migrant remittances between the US and Mexico. This country case study is particularly apt as there is sizeable labour migration from Mexico to the US, from where remittances will be sent home. It is discovered that children from migrant households complete significantly more years of education. Specifically, girls will receive an estimated additional 0.23 to 0.89 years of schooling (Hanson & Woodruff (2003)). Researching El Salvador, Cox & Ureta (2003) is another important paper which concludes that remittances have a large, significant impact on school retention. Additionally, Chowdhury (2014) finds that remittances in Bangladesh noticeably boost personal savings. This leads to a considerable decrease in poverty levels, a rise in per capita income and allows for the provision of advanced education. In line with these results, Mansour et al (2011) shows empirically that migrant remittances positively influence educational prospects in Jordan.

The most accepted theory to explain these observations is that households wish to send their children to school but are unable to do so due to financial constraints. Incoming remittances relax household budget constraints by raising incomes, allowing households to increase education expenditures which will promote attainment. Another promising argument is the brain-gain effect (Contreras (2013)). As remittances increase, the return to emigration in turn rises. This increase in prospects will motivate households to better educate their children to capture the rising returns to labour emigration.

The existing analysis goes further by exploring the effect by both gender and age. Bansak & Chezum (2009) focus on the differences of remittances on human capital formation between boys and girls in Nepal. They conclude that the human capital of boys benefits more from remittances than their female counterparts. This may be because in developing countries, where gender roles are more rigid, it is the expectation of boys to be future household-earners whereas girls will have more family-oriented responsibilities. Hence, more focus is placed on educating boys to improve their future employment prospects. El-Aziz & Sami (2018) focus on Egypt and distinguish between two age categories: school-aged and university-aged. Their findings conclude a positive effect of remittances on the educational attainment of university-aged individuals but no impact on school-aged individuals. Studying Ghana, Gyimah-Brempong & Asiedu (2015) find that remittances are more likely to be funnelled into education spending if the head of the household is female. These studies serve to prove the importance of incorporating different socioeconomic considerations into any analysis, as different effects will be realised depending on individual background.

However, not all existing studies show an effect of remittances on education. Focusing on Indonesia, Nguyen & Purnamasari (2011) could not find evidence through their regression that migrant remittances increase school enrolment of the household's children. This conclusion was also reached by Acosta (2011), who could only discover a very weak impact of remittances on educational attainment.

Other papers fall into the camp of a negative relationship. The most prominent study that concludes this is by McKenzie & Rapoport (2011), who discover a strong inverse relationship between remittances and the educational attainment of the children. This notion is confirmed by Köllner (2013), who finds that in Tajikistan, receiving remittances negatively influences educational attainment for higher, non-mandatory education. The proposed explanation of this differing finding is that faced with the choice between labour migration and higher education, the children of migrant families will be more likely to pursue migration themselves. This could be because they are inspired by relatives, and perhaps can see better the financial benefits of migration. Hence, they will drop out of school to pursue international labour opportunities. This concept is similar to the proposed brain-gain idea, but instead, individuals are capturing the returns to migration immediately, without the initial need for further investment into their education.

To precisely determine the influence of remittances on educational attainment, most of the existing literature uses an Instrumental Variable (IV) estimation (Bansak & Chezum (2009); Mansour et al (2011); McKenzie & Rapoport (2011); Nguyen & Purnamasari (2011); Köllner (2013)). This estimation mitigates any potential endogeneity or reverse causality between our variables of interest. For example, if a child is enrolled in education, more remittances from family abroad may be sent to fund this expense. I will use an IV estimation in this paper to determine a causal effect of receiving remittances on educational prospects. Different studies also explore varying types of data. Some literature utilises country-level data to determine differing results between countries (Dustmann & Speciale (2006); Fajnzylber & López (2008); Mohammed (2022)). Alternatively, other papers have made use of micro level data to find variation between individual households in a country (Sabur & Mahmud (2008); El Aziz & Sami (2018)). This study will employ the latter by using the 2014-2015 Liberian Household Income and Expenditure Survey. I will use this cross-sectional data to determine the relationship at a fixed period in time. This method is in line with other papers (Cox & Ureta (2003); Bansak & Chezum (2009); McKenzie & Rapoport (2011)).

Much of the literature to date has focused on developing nations in Asia and Latin America. However, to date, there has been much less emphasis on exploring the relationship between remittances and educational attainment in Sub-Saharan Africa. One plausible reason for this gap is due to a lack of available data for use in these nations as opposed to their Asian or Latin American counterparts. One existing paper on this region is by Gyimah-Brempong & Asiedu (2015), who use cross-section and pseudo-panel data to investigate the effect in Ghana. They conclude a strong and significant impact of international remittances on the probability of both primary and secondary school enrolment. This paper will be of particular importance to this study on Liberia due to the assumed socioeconomic similarities between the two West African countries. The contribution of my research will be to build on the existing stock of knowledge regarding the influence of remittances on educational attainment, but with a particular focus on a region of the world which has, up until now, been relatively unrepresented in the literature.

The existing literature on Liberia has focused on remittance-based growth (Kruah (2017)) and the effect of post-conflict diaspora on current development (Dipeolu (2023)). Pfeiffer (2013) focuses on the role of remittances on post-war construction in Liberia and offers suggestions to better utilise remittance flows to improve Liberia's economic situation. Despite this research, there is still a noticeable gap in the literature dedicated to the role of remittances on educational attainment which my paper aims to fill.

3. Background on Liberia

Liberia was founded in 1822 as an outpost for freed slaves returning from the Americas (Dennis (2006)). The colony would become the second black republic in the world at the time, after Haiti (Office of the Historian (n.d.)). Liberia became an independent sovereign state in 1847, following its independence from the American Colonization Society. Despite its short history, Liberia has experienced significant turmoil, including two devastating civil wars from 1989 to 2003, which led to widespread destruction and human rights violations. In recent years, the country has made strides towards rebuilding but still grapples with the challenges of economic development and governance. Rubber and timber have been the main exports since the end of the civil war, earning approximately \$170 million annually (Migiro (2019)). Mining is also a large industry in Liberia, contributing to around 11.0% of the country's GDP in 2013 (Migiro (2019)).

Poverty is widespread in Liberia, with 50.9% of the population living below the national poverty line in 2016 and 27.6% classified as living in extreme poverty (World Bank Group (2023)). Food vulnerability is also prevalent, which could have a key impact on the results of this study. If food expenditure is the primary focus

of household spending, then in general, remittances could be spent on necessary sustenance rather than on human capital investment.

The historic connection between Liberia and the United States has led to a key migration pattern. Migration of Liberians to the U.S. peaked in the 1990s during the two civil wars as Liberians searched for refuge from the conflict. Due to this migration link, an estimated 100,000 Liberians are living in the United States as of 2022 (REMITSCOPE (2022)). This connection is vividly illustrated through remittances. In 2021, Liberia received an estimated 65.7% of their total remittance value from the United States (KNOMAD (2021)). This contribution from the Liberian diaspora in the U.S. highlights the connection between the two countries and the importance it has on the Liberian economy. Moreover, Liberia's interesting history and current remittance landscape make it a relevant country to use as a case study to observe the relationship between remittances and educational attainment.

4. Schooling in Liberia

During the civil wars, the formal education system was almost non-existent in Liberia (Ministry of Education, (2016)). Since 2003, the Ministry of Education (MoE) in Liberia has worked to develop the education system, attempting to provide access to education for all citizens. Education in Liberia is structured into four main stages. Firstly, there is Early Childhood Education (ECE) providing for ages 3-5. Next, there is Basic (Primary) Education for ages 6-14. Then there is Senior Secondary Education for ages 15-17, and finally, there is Higher Education which provides for students older than 18. Despite the MoE's efforts, there exists wealth-based inequality in educational access, especially at higher stages. As of 2015, there were 5,178 primary schools in Liberia, with 2,494 being public, 1,558 private, 822 faith-based and 304 being community-run (Ministry of Education, (2016)). Private schooling represents only 30% of all schools for children aged 6-14, meaning that the majority of schools for this age range are accessible to families irrespective of wealth. However, this is not the case for senior secondary schooling as out of the 640 senior schools, only 144 are public (Ministry of Education, (2016)). Most non-governmental schools (private and faith-based) require attendance fees, which will prevent the children of poorer households accessing them. For poorer families, school fees and the indirect cost of education are the primary reasons children and young people do not go to school (Ministry of Education, (2016)). There is also geographical inequality of educational access. The majority of private schools are located in the more populous regions (Montserrado, Nimba, Margribi). This highlights an urban-rural divide to educational accessibility, which will be experienced negatively by those living in rural communities.

Both income and geographical inequalities are evident in school enrolment rates. Only 86.7% of age-appropriate children are enrolled in primary education. This percentage falls to 52.7% for lower secondary, and 39.4% for upper secondary (Ministry of Education, (2016)). This decline in enrolment rate as students get older is evidence of increasing financial requirements for later education stages preventing poorer households from access. These observations would suggest that remittances will have less of an impact on educational attainment for younger students due to better relative provision of costless government-run schools. They also suggest that there should be a greater impact on attainment for children aged 15 and older.

Education in Liberia is financed through government expenditure, development partners and education fees. In 2015, government education expenditure was 2.1% of Liberia's GDP, which ranks Liberia 169th out of 176 countries that the World Bank recorded this data for (The World Bank (2023)). Overall, Liberia remains on the lower end of relative educational spending and compares poorly with surrounding countries. This has resulted in the underfunding of the majority of schools (Ministry of Education, (2016)). This underfunding

into education, coinciding with other factors including teacher absenteeism, means that the quality of education in government-run schools is low and students do not achieve the intended learning development to make them employable as adults.

5. Methodology

5.1 Data

The data used is taken from the 2014-2015 Liberian Household Income and Expenditure Survey (HIES). This survey was conducted by the Liberia Institute for Statistics and Geo-Information Services (LISGIS) and was sponsored among others by the Government of Liberia and the World Bank (The World Bank (2016)). The HIES consists of 4,082 households and 18,089 individuals. The data covers a wide scope including household and individual information regarding education, health, employment and more. My analysis will specifically utilise the sections on education and international cash transfers to investigate the effect of receiving remittances on educational attainment. From this data, the subset of individuals aged 6-24 years old will be used in the empirical study. This chosen age range is in line with most studies as it is assumed to cover the ages when people tend to be in education (Köllner (2013)). The upper-age boundary was not capped at 21 to account for potential over-age students who have enrolled in their education level later than the intended age. This age range contains 7,442 observations which will be used in my study.

5.2 Descriptive Statistics

The dependent variable of this study was chosen to be current school enrolment at any level. This variable has been widely accepted and utilised in existing survey-based papers as a good reflection of educational attainment (Bansak & Chezum (2009); Gyimah-Brempong & Asiedu (2015)). The variable is binary, taking a value of 1 if the individual was currently enrolled in school at the time of the survey and a value of 0 if not.

There are two independent variables of interest. First, a binary variable indicating whether or not a household has received remittances in the last 12 months and second, the value of household remittances received in the last 12 months. Many existing studies use a binary variable of remittance receipt (Gyimah-Brempong & Asiedu (2015); El-Aziz & Sami (2018)). However, in addition, I will also utilise the continuous data of the value of remittances received as it is believed that this will provide a greater understanding of the relationship between remittances and educational attainment. The value of remittances provided in the survey was in two units: US dollars and Liberian dollars. For the purpose of uniformity, all values in US dollars were converted into Liberian dollars at the exchange rate at the time of the survey. A common criticism of using the value of remittances received is the possibility for individuals surveyed to misremember the correct value received (Gyimah-Brempong & Asiedu (2015)). Despite this concern, it will still be useful to investigate this relationship, as it may be the case that the quantity of remittances received is important to school enrolment as well as just receiving remittances. The survey provided detail on incoming household monetary transfers both nationally and internationally. I decided to focus on the effect of international remittances in particular.

The gender of the individual was provided by the survey and takes the form of a binary variable with male = 1, female = 0. Whether the individual's father and mother are alive are also binary variables which will be included in the model with alive = 1, dead = 0. The highest education level reached by the respective parent of the individual was also recorded and is characterised as: 0 = No schooling, 1 = Some elementary schooling, 2 = Completed elementary schooling, 3 = Some junior schooling, 4 = Completed junior schooling, 5 = Some senior schooling, 6 = Completed senior schooling, 7 = More than senior school. Other included variables are

classified into three categories: individual characteristics, household characteristics and regional characteristics. All of the variables used are described in Table 1, and Table 2 provides the summary statistics for the full sample.

Table 1: Variable Description

Variable	Description	Type
Individual Characteristics		
gender	= 1 if male	binary
age	individual age	discrete
age_squared	individual age squared	discrete
rural_urban	= 1 if lives in an urban area	binary
father_alive	= 1 if father is alive	binary
mother_alive	= 1 if mother is alive	binary
father_educ	highest education achieved by father	discrete
mother_educ	highest education achieved by mother	discrete
laboured	= 1 if laboured in the last 12 months	binary
Household Characteristics		
binary_remitt	= 1 if received remittances in the last 12 months	binary
remitt_value	value of remittances received in the last 12 months	continuous
car	= 1 if household owns a car	binary
children	number of children in household	discrete
adults	number of adults in household	discrete
log_labour_income	log of income received from labour in the last 12 months	continuous
Regional Characteristics		
people_per_school	a ratio of population to schools in a certain region	continuous
avg_house_size	average household size in a certain region	continuous

The number of children living in the household at the time of the survey was calculated as the number of individuals aged 18 or younger whilst adults were classified as anyone older than 18. The data provided the monetary value of labour provided in the individual's last payment. This payment was then scaled up to cover the last 12 months and pooled across the entire household to indicate the total labour income for the household in the last year. The regional data was taken from the 2022 Liberia Population and Housing Census (LISGIS (2022)). Despite this data being newer than the household survey used, it is assumed that the regional characteristics of Liberia have not changed significantly in the interim.

Table 2: Statistics Summary

Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Individual Characteristics				
gender	0.50	0.50	-	1.00
age	13.19	5.37	6.00	24.00
age_squared	202.70	156.70	36.00	576.00
rural_urban	0.41	0.49	-	1.00
father_alive	0.90	0.29	-	1.00
mother_alive	0.96	0.19	-	1.00
father_educ	1.21	2.28	-	7.00
mother_educ	0.32	1.18	-	7.00
laboured	0.41	0.49	-	1.00
Household Characteristics				
binary_remitt	0.12	0.32	-	1.00
remitt_value	5,382.00	29,310.00	-	486,000.00
car	0.01	0.13	-	1.00
children	3.70	2.02	-	20.00
adults	2.48	1.29	-	14.00
log_labour_income	11.75	0.95	-	17.38
Regional Characteristics				
people_per_school	827.50	114.20	662.70	1,019.00
avg_house_size	4.53	0.49	3.50	5.30

The mean education level of both fathers and mothers is very low, highlighting the poor historical state of Liberia's education system. This problem could have been exacerbated by the civil wars which greatly disrupted the nation's stability and would have prevented the previous generation – now parents – from accessing a higher level of education. There is also a clear disparity between the attained educational levels of fathers and mothers. This perceived male-biased gender gap towards education attainment is common in developing nations as priority is given to males compared with their female counterparts.

In the data set, approximately 43% of individuals aged 6-24 are currently enrolled in school. This relatively low figure is reflective of the current landscape outlined in the *Schooling in Liberia* section. School attendance percentage by age group is depicted in Table 3.

Table 3: Enrolment Rates by Age Category

Age Range	Number in Sample	Currently Enrolled	Enrolment Percentage
6-9	2408	352	0.15
10-13	1811	1010	0.56
14-17	1401	1041	0.74
18-21	1078	549	0.51
22-24	744	217	0.29
Total	7442	3169	0.43

The rate of enrolment varies noticeably by age group. The lowest percentage is for the 6-9 age group with just a 15% rate of school enrolment. This can be explained by the prevalence of over-age students in Liberia, who start their education later than the appropriate age. The gradual increase in enrolment rates up to the 14-17

subgroup which is succeeded by a fall-off is expected and logical as older students will be faced with employment opportunities both domestically and abroad.

5.3 The Model

The models I use in this research assume that households in Liberia are faced with a resource constraint that binds their expenditures. This concept is widely accepted (Acosta (2011); Contreras (2013); Gyimah-Brempong & Asiedu (2015)). The data provided by the HIES allows me to investigate the impacts of international remittances on school attendance holding account of individual, household and region-specific characteristics. As is the case with many low-income countries, we can assume that Liberian households face relatively tight resource constraints, with the priority of the household being to meet subsistence needs (Food, Water, Housing). It can also be assumed that households will wish to educate their children to an adequate level, either due to direct altruism or in an attempt to increase human capital and subsequently future earnings. Despite this desire, tight budget constraints may necessitate the neglect of education spending on children in favour of meeting the more current issue of subsistence requirements. Hence any relaxation in resource constraint experienced by the household may lift household income above basic subsistence needs to a level that allows them to spend money on tuition fees, books, stationary etc. The relaxant of focus in this study is remittances, which if received by a household to a high enough degree, will allow them to increase education spending on offspring, increasing their probability of educational attainment.

Moreover, it is hypothesised that there is a positive relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables of focus conditional on other factors (X, Y, Z). Mathematically, the models take the form:

$$enrol = \beta_0 + \beta_1 binary_remitt + \beta_2 X + \beta_3 Y + \beta_4 Z + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

$$enrol = \beta_0 + \beta_1 remitt_value + \beta_2 X + \beta_3 Y + \beta_4 Z + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

Where X = individual characteristics, Y = household characteristics and Z = region-specific characteristics.

The dependent variable *enrol* is binary and provided for each individual by the data set. The independent variables of interest, remittance receipt (*binary_remitt*) and value of remittances received (*remitt_value*) are also provided for each household by the data set. The control variables used in the model are in line with previous research and are also provided by the data set. A full explanation of each variable is shown in Table 1. Finally, the equations that are estimated are described as:

$$enrol = \beta_0 + \beta_1 binary_remitt + \beta_2 gender + \beta_3 age + \beta_4 age_squared + \beta_5 rural_urban + \beta_6 father_alive + \beta_7 mother_alive + \beta_8 father_educ + \beta_9 mother_educ + \beta_{10} laboured + \beta_{11} car + \beta_{12} children + \beta_{13} adults + \beta_{14} log_labour_income + \beta_{15} people_per_school + \beta_{16} avg_house_size + \varepsilon \quad (3)$$

$$enrol = \beta_0 + \beta_1 remitt_value + \beta_2 gender + \beta_3 age + \beta_4 age_squared + \beta_5 rural_urban + \beta_6 father_alive + \beta_7 mother_alive + \beta_8 father_educ + \beta_9 mother_educ + \beta_{10} laboured + \beta_{11} car + \beta_{12} children + \beta_{13} adults + \beta_{14} log_labour_income + \beta_{15} people_per_school + \beta_{16} avg_house_size + \varepsilon \quad (4)$$

5.4 Estimation Method

If the variables of interest were exogenous, a standard probit estimator would suffice. Probit regressions are nonlinear models specifically designed for binary dependent variables (Stock & Watson (2020)). However, as widely accepted in the literature, there is potential for endogeneity between remittances and educational attainment which could lead to unreliable estimations. There is also the possibility of reverse causality where more money is sent from abroad to fund existing educational enrolment. To account for these possibilities, I introduce an Instrumental Variable (IV) estimation. In keeping with the two conditions for instrument validity, the instruments used must be relevant and exogenous (Stock & Watson (2020)). In this context, an acceptable instrument will affect international remittances but have no direct influence on individual school enrolment. A widely used IV is existing migration patterns (Köllner (2013); El-Aziz & Sami (2018)). However, this information was not available for the country of focus in my study. In existing country studies where migration data is more scarce, other instruments have been used including distance to the nearest office and rainfall shocks (Gyimah-Brempong & Asiedu (2015)). I will employ the distance to the main Liberian airport (*dis_air*) and the number of months in the past year the household head has been at home (*head_attend*) as instruments for remittances. From my initial analysis, it is found that distance to the main airport is negatively and significantly related to both remittance variables. This finding is expected; the further away a household is from Liberia's main airport, the less likely they are to have individuals abroad sending money home. This instrument also has no direct effect on enrolment, only an indirect effect through international remittances. Hence, this chosen instrument meets the accepted criteria and will be applicable.

The main airport in Liberia is Roberts International Airport which services Liberia's capital city, Monrovia. An average distance to the airport was calculated by region and then assigned to each individual in the study. Utilising the algorithms and geographical data of Google Maps, an average point in each region was decided. The distance between this and the airport was then calculated in miles following the shortest driving route.

I found that the household head's attendance has a positive and significant effect on both remittance variables. This result was not initially expected but can be easily explained. It was originally believed that a household head may spend less time at home due to work commitments, potentially abroad from where they would send home remittances. However, the positive and significant impact indicates a different relationship. The presence of the household head at home likely facilitates better coordination and trust in managing remittances. Contrary to the initial expectation, the household head's attendance enhances the flow of remittances through the creation of a secure environment which encourages financial contributions from relatives abroad. Finally, I argue that there is no direct relationship between the household head's attendance over the last 12 months and a child's current school enrolment.

To investigate equations (3) and (4), an IV probit estimator is used. In particular, I will be employing the `-ivprobit-` command in Stata. The estimates of the IV probit estimator are displayed in Table 4.

6. Empirical Results

The estimation may be influenced by heteroskedasticity. If heteroskedasticity is present, as is a common occurrence in the literature, it can result in biased standard errors and incorrect inferences about the model. To account for this possibility, robust standard errors were used.

Table 4: Marginal Effects with Robust Standard Errors

Variable	Marginal Effects			
	Equation 3: binary_remitt as indep. Var		Equation 4: remitt_value as indep. Var	
	Standard Probit	IV Probit	Standard Probit	IV Probit
<i>gender</i>	0.071*** (0.161)	0.075*** (0.169)	0.072*** (0.160)	0.092*** (0.021)
<i>age</i>	0.256*** (0.007)	0.259*** (0.008)	0.255*** (0.007)	0.250*** (0.011)
<i>age_squared</i>	-0.008*** (0.000)	-0.008*** (0.000)	-0.008*** (0.000)	-0.008*** (0.000)
<i>rural_urban</i>	0.076*** (0.017)	0.039 (0.027)	0.077*** (0.017)	0.013 (0.030)
<i>father_alive</i>	0.073** (0.030)	0.076** (0.032)	0.069** (0.031)	0.052 (0.042)
<i>mother_alive</i>	-0.01 (0.047)	-0.032 (0.050)	-0.006 (0.047)	-0.017 (0.052)
<i>father_educ</i>	-0.001 (0.004)	-0.006 (0.005)	-0.001 (0.004)	-0.013* (0.004)
<i>mother_educ</i>	0.021*** (0.006)	0.015** (0.007)	0.021*** (0.006)	0.008 (0.010)
<i>laboured</i>	-0.003 (0.020)	0.000 (0.025)	-0.029 (0.198)	0.124 (0.029)
<i>binary_remitt</i>	0.063** (0.026)	0.410** (0.195)	N/A	N/A
<i>remitt_value</i>	N/A	N/A	9.71E-07*** (3.66E-07)	1.18E-04** (4.02E-06)
<i>car</i>	0.077* (0.045)	0.071 (0.049)	0.084* (0.046)	0.136*** (0.049)
<i>children</i>	0.010** (0.005)	0.005 (0.005)	0.010** (0.005)	0.003 (0.006)
<i>adults</i>	0.005 (0.007)	0.006 (0.007)	0.004 (0.007)	0.002 (0.007)
<i>log_labour_income</i>	0.031*** (0.009)	0.017 (0.012)	0.031*** (0.009)	0.002 (0.015)
<i>people_per_school</i>	0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)
<i>avg_house_size</i>	0.012 (0.017)	0.015 (0.017)	0.012 (0.017)	0.014 (0.019)
Number of Observations	7,442	7,442	7,442	7,442
Pseudo R-Squared				
<i>McFadden</i>	0.242	0.241	0.243	0.241
<i>McKelvey and Zavoina</i>	0.429	0.428	0.432	0.428
Instrument Tests				
<i>Wald test of exogeneity (p-value)</i>		0.06		0.0008
<i>F statistic</i>		18.66		8.60
<i>Amemiya-Lee-Newey test (p-value)</i>		0.0517		0.5459

Average Marginal Effects (AMEs) displayed from probit and ivprobit regressions. Number of observations in each regression shown. Values from two goodness-of-fit measures are displayed. The Wald test of Exogeneity tests the null hypothesis that suspected endogenous regressors are exogenous. The value displayed is the p-value of the test. The F statistics displayed is from the first-stage regression and is used to assess instrument strength. The Amemiya-Lee-Newey test assesses overidentifying restrictions and instrument validity. The value displayed is the p-value of the test. Standard errors in parentheses; *** p<0.1; ** p<0.05; * p<0.1.

Before looking at the main results from the regression table, the validity and strength of the instruments used will be discussed. The regression statistics analysing the instruments are displayed at the bottom of Table 4. Firstly, I conducted a Wald test of exogeneity to statistically determine whether the independent variables in the models were correlated with the error term, questioning their presumed exogeneity (Wald (1943)). The null hypothesis of the test is that the suspected endogenous regressors are exogenous. In both IV models ran, the p-values from the Wald test were significant at the 10% level. This outcome means that there is statistical evidence for the null hypothesis of variable exogeneity to be rejected. The significant findings imply that the independent variables used are indeed correlated with the error term and an IV approach is justified.

Next, the F statistics obtained from the regression can be used to assess instrument strength. Unfortunately, there is no appropriate rules-of-thumb for the F statistic when the structural model is nonlinear, but one suggested benchmark is the Stock-Yogo recommendations (Wooldridge (2014)). The F statistics gathered both exceed the threshold of 7.03 recommended by Stock & Yogo (2005) at the 10% maximal size level, indicating that the instruments are likely not weak according to the guideline. Nonetheless, it is important to remember that the F-statistic I refer to is the overall F-statistic for the first-stage regression rather than a specific F-test for the excluded instruments. This is significant because the overall F-statistic will not be as precise and accurate at determining instrument strength as a dedicated test would. Unfortunately, given the limitations, this overall F-statistic serves as our best available metric for evaluating instrument strength. In addition, the first-stage estimates of the excluded instruments are shown in Table 5. While presenting the first-stage coefficients is not a perfect test for instrument strength, it is used in existing literature (Gyimah-Brempong & Asiedu (2015)). Hence, while proceeding with caution, the evidence suggests that the instruments are strong enough to provide reliable IV estimates.

Table 5: First-Stage Regression Results

Variable	Coefficients	
	<i>binary_remitt</i>	<i>remitt_value</i>
<i>dis_air</i>	-0.001*** (0.000)	-17.187** (7.525)
<i>head_attend</i>	0.009* (0.005)	1088.624** (453.000)

Holding account all other covariates. Standard errors in parentheses; *** p<0.1; ** p<0.05; * p<0.1.

Finally, to test for overidentifying restrictions, I conducted an Amemiya-Lee-Newey (ALN) test. This test, which was originally developed by (Amemiya (1978)) and later studied by (Newey (1987)) and (Lee (1992)), is applicable in testing instrument validity in non-linear models. The null hypothesis of the test is that the instruments used are valid, meaning they are not correlated with the error term of the model. At the 5% significance level, a p-value greater than 0.05 suggests that there is not enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The p-values for both models exceed this benchmark, indicating that I fail to reject the null hypothesis and there is no statistical evidence to doubt the validity of the instruments used. Overall, the tests I completed indicate the need for instrumental use, and that the instruments used are valid.

Table 4 presents two widely used goodness-of-fit measures: McFadden (1973) and McKelvey & Zavoina (1975) respectively. Both pseudo R-Squared values were displayed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the models' explanatory power. McFadden's pseudo R-Squared is shown to have a downward bias (Veall & Zimmermann (1996)) when compared to what would be expected in an OLS regression. A common rule of thumb in the literature is that McFadden pseudo R-Squared values between 0.2 and 0.4 are indicative of an

extremely good fit (Louviere (2000)). The values produced by the models, ranging from 0.241 to 0.243, are well within this boundary, signifying that a good proportion of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables in the models. McKelvey and Zavoina's pseudo R-Squared is regarded as a good fit for limited dependent variables (Veall & Zimmermann (1996)) and the values generated are more in line with OLS regressions. The values provided by this pseudo R-Squared measure also indicate that the models have strong goodness-of-fit.

Average Marginal Effects (AMEs) were used to analyse the outcome of the regressions. This method is recommended by Wooldridge (2020), who argues that AMEs offer a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of explanatory variables on the dependent variable across the entire sample, rather than at a specific point such as the mean of the explanatory variables. By using AMEs, my results will be reflective of the average effect experienced by individuals in the survey, thus highlighting the applicability and reliability of the findings. My interpretation is inspired by and in line with Perrailon et al (2021) who outlines the correct method to interpret marginal effects and states that marginal effects are indispensable when it comes to nonlinear model interpretations. In keeping with Perrailon et al (2021), marginal effects were gathered using the `-margins-` command in Stata. As stated by Perrailon et al (2021), marginal effects pertain to the expected change in the dependent variable for a small change in a continuous predictor, while incremental effects denote the change when a binary predictor shifts from 0 to 1. Perrailon et al (2021) also mentions how the term marginal effect can refer to both. For simplicity and to maintain consistency, I have chosen to refer to the effects of all variables uniformly as marginal effects.

The coefficient on remittance receipt (*binary_remitt*) suggests a positive and significant marginal effect on school enrolment probabilities for both models. From running the standard probit model, receiving remittances, *ceteris paribus*, is correlated with a 6 percentage point increase in the likelihood of being currently enrolled in education. Using an IV estimation, it was found that receiving remittances leads to individuals being 40 percentage points more likely to be currently enrolled. Compared to the other determinants of enrolment, receiving remittances is one of the key influences on enrolment probabilities. This relatively large relationship is in line with Gyimah-Brempong & Asiedu (2015), who find that receiving remittances in Ghana increases enrolment probabilities for secondary school students by 50 percentage points. This parallel was expected due to the socioeconomic similarities between the two West African countries.

The coefficients on the value of remittances received (*remitt_value*) in both models are also positive and significant. Whilst the effects found may not seem large, the unit of choice was Liberian Dollars, which varied significantly between households. Going further, I followed the guideline set by Perrailon et al (2021) in finding and interpreting marginal effects at varying values of an independent variable. Firstly, I found the probability of enrolment at differing remittance values, keeping account of the other covariates. I next computed the difference between these enrolment probabilities to determine the effect of varying levels of remittances. I found that a one standard deviation increase in remittance value received over not receiving anything increases enrolment probabilities by approximately 30 percentage points, whilst a two standard deviation increase raises probability by 47 percentage points. A graphical representation of the increase in the likelihood of enrolment at differing remittance values is shown in Figure 1. This figure shows the increase in probability over not receiving any remittances (i.e., All things being equal, receiving remittances totalling 20,000 LRB will increase the probability of a student being enrolled by approximately 22 percentage points over a student who does not receive remittances).

Figure 1: The Increase in Probability of Enrolment for Varying Remittance Values

The figure demonstrates that increases in the value of remittances received will increase the probability of enrolment. Interestingly however, this is happening at a decreasing rate. Given the assumed high priority placed on education by households, once their financial needs for subsistence are met, households will allocate additional income to educational expenses. At a certain level of receipt, the household will have sufficient funds to meet necessary requirements and pay for education. Any remittances received past this point will not be likely to significantly enhance the probability of enrolment. Hence, the findings suggest evidence of diminishing returns of remittances on education attainment, which is a relationship that has not previously been focused on in the existing literature.

The results from the two independent variables of interest show a significant relationship between remittances and educational attainment. This finding is in line with this study's hypothesis that remittance receipt relaxes the household budget constraint above a subsistence level, allowing for more educational expenditures, all things being equal. Whilst this verdict bridges a gap in understanding this region of the world, it does align with existing studies focused on other areas (Hanson & Woodruff (2003); Cox & Ureta (2003); Gyimah-Brempong & Asiedu (2015)).

To analyse the effects of remittances further, the models were regressed by age following the methodology outlined by Perrillon (2021). The observed marginal effects, shown in Figure 2, do not align with theoretical expectations. It is observed that when using remittance receipt (*binary_remitt*) as the independent variable, remittances have a nonlinear effect on current enrolment by age. This finding is not expected in the case of Liberia as the relative scarcity of government-funded schools for higher education would be expected to increase the impact of remittances on older students' enrolment. From the graph, it is clear that the AMEs of remittances peak around age 9 before declining gradually. This decline may be because as students get older, their households choose to have them start working, valuing their immediate earnings over further education, even when receiving remittances. The study by El-Aziz & Sami (2018) finds a greater, positive influence of

remittances on university-aged students compared to school-aged students in Egypt, contrary to the age-varying marginal effects discovered by my research. This intriguing difference underpins the complexity of remittances' role in education and highlights the importance of further targeted research to better understand this relationship.

Figure 2: AME of Remittance Receipt (*binary_remitt*) on education by the age of the individual

The analysis also provides interesting insight into how other characteristics affect enrolment probabilities. Firstly, the educational gender gap is clear, significant and consistent across all models. All things being equal, I found that being male increases the probability of an individual being currently enrolled in education by between 7-9 percentage points. This is reflective of the higher priority placed on educating male children for the goal of obtaining better career prospects in the future. My result aligns with other studies that have a larger focus on gender as a key determinant in schooling rates in developing nations. I also found that in the sample used, age increases the probability of enrolment at a decreasing rate. This finding is expected due to the high rates of over-age students in Liberia. Living in an urban area is also found to have a consistently positive influence on enrolment probabilities. This is intuitive as it reflects the urban-rural education divide prevalent in Liberia, where there is a higher proportion of schools in the nation's more developed areas.

The marginal effects of the parental characteristics (*father_alive*, *mother_alive*, *father_educ*, *mother_educ*) provide a partly unexpected insight. *Ceteris paribus*, an individual's father being alive increases the probability of enrolment by 5-7 percentage points. This was an expected outcome as having a father alive will in most cases increase household stability and income, subsequently increasing the probability of education enrolment. A similar result was expected for the individual's mother. However, across all models conducted, the coefficients were negative and not statistically significant. Given the lack of statistical significance and that the mother being alive is not an area of focus in the study, this unexpected coefficient does not warrant substantial interpretation. However, I believe more targeted research should be undertaken to understand this relationship with greater accuracy. An unexpected and mostly insignificant coefficient was also found on father's education, but due to the same reasoning outlined before, no important interpretation will be given to this result in this particular study. The marginal effect of mother's education is positive and significant across most of the models, which was an expected outcome. This result is evidence of inter-generational educational persistence within households, where the benefits of education are passed down from adult to child, through increased household incomes or other means.

The positive and statistically significant marginal effects for household car ownership suggest a 7-14 percentage point increase in the likelihood of school enrolment, underscoring the importance of transportation in educational access. Car ownership enables travel to schools beyond immediate localities, thereby expanding educational opportunities for individuals. Owning a car is also representative of household wealth. If a household can afford to own and run a car, it follows that they will be more likely to pay to educate their children. Finally, a positive and significant marginal effect of labour income is intuitive as an increase in this

variable will relax the household budget constraint and facilitate more educational investment for the household's children.

7. Policy Recommendations

This research's key finding is that the data indicates a positive relationship between both receiving remittances and the value of this receipt on the probability of educational attainment in Liberia. This verdict has important policy implications that representatives in Liberia should be informed of. In January 2024, Liberia saw a change in leadership as Joseph Boakai replaced incumbent George Weah as the nation's president. One of the cornerstones of Boakai's presidential campaign was his plan to introduce measures to promote human capacity development (The Joe Boakai Plan (2023)). To summarise the plan, Boakai wishes to strengthen society and the private sector through developments in human capital. To achieve this, Boakai will be focusing on improving the education system by getting more young people involved in learning requisite skills for the job market. The education and human capital of the population is an area of concern for Liberia. In 2020, Liberia ranked in the bottom five countries of the World Human Capital Index (HCI) which combines measures for survival, health and importantly education (The World Bank (2020)). Hence, Boakai's focus on improving the education system is appropriate and needed. With this goal in mind, my findings are of particular relevance to Liberia's current climate.

To assist in their aspirations, Liberian policymakers should introduce measures to encourage the international workers in the diaspora to increase the flow and value of the remittances that they send home. Through introducing these measures, the human capital of Liberia's youth can be expected to increase due to the relationship determined. One such policy could be to attempt to reduce the cost of remittance transaction fees. Whilst individual data is not available on Liberia's average transaction cost, Sub-Saharan Africa remains the most expensive region to send money to as of Q3 2023 (The World Bank (2023)). The World Bank recorded an average cost of 7.39% for the region compared with the global average of 6.18%. If it is assumed that Liberia's average transaction cost is in line with its region, then there exists space for Liberia to introduce policies to curb the high rates. This will encourage not only more remittance flows but that more of the existing flow reaching households.

Whilst much of the existing literature focuses directly on the impact of remittances on domestic improvement, there has been important analysis conducted in regard to how to encourage and optimise remittance flows through policy measures. One such paper is Carling (2004) which outlines and explains a range of policy measures to enhance the impact of remittances on development. Whilst this paper does not directly reflect on domestic education, the policies outlined are suited and can be tailored in a way to be relevant to the findings of my research. One measure outlined is tax breaks on remittances. With this, the government would be incentivising the channelling of remittances into education investment by allowing more remittances to reach households for spending on school fees.

On the other hand, another proposed policy is the taxation of emigrant's remittances. This may be preferred by the government if they would favour having a direct influence on education. The measure would be effective only if it is ensured that the revenue generated is spent effectively on improving educational institutions and subsidising costs. However, The World Bank (2006) argues that measures to tax migrant remittance flows inevitably disincentivise total remittances sent. Therefore, I advise that this is not the best measure to introduce in the attempt to improve domestic human capital, as it will lead to fewer household remittances received and a subsequent reduction in household education spending. On this point, Brown (2006) argues the case for avoiding remittance taxation altogether to incentivise higher flows. The government

should be careful to not introduce any measures that discourage remittance flows due to the relationship determined between remittances and educational attainment.

Additionally, the government could aim to secure future remittances by promoting transnationalism, diaspora management and continued migration. Whilst there might not be clear policy measures to address this aim, government initiatives to improve migrant networks, international job opportunities, and support for citizens living abroad can be expected to increase future remittance flows. (Brown, 2006) outlines the importance of migrant worker programs between countries, such as Pakistani migrants working in Saudi Arabia. If Liberia could set up long-standing relationships with other nations in need of workers, then this would increase the probability of Liberians finding viable work abroad. This process will also have the additional benefit of improving the skills of Liberian workers who will be better trained by more developed countries with greater labour practices. This benefit will be felt if these migrant workers return home to contribute to the domestic labour market.

8. A Comment on Educational Quality

The research presented so far has focused solely on the realised relationship between remittances and educational attainment, and how the new Liberian government can utilise this information to assist in their domestic goals. However, it must be noted that improving enrolment is just one aspect to combating the ongoing issue. The quality of education offered by the state and private institutions is vital in determining the level of knowledge and skills possessed by Liberia's youth. Currently, the Liberian education system faces many quality-related challenges such as an undersupply of teacher and learning materials (TLM) and a high rate of unqualified teachers (Ministry of Education (2022)). Specifically, as of 2022, Liberia had an average teacher-trained percentage of only 45%, well below the Sub-Saharan average of 68% (Ministry of Education (2022)). To indicate the lack of learning materials, in mathematics and science, Liberia averages eight students per textbook, limiting the learning capabilities of students (Ministry of Education (2022)). Also, the facilities offered by Liberian schools are inadequate to meet the needs of their students. Most notably, the average female-to-toilet rate of 55 is an issue for female students' hygiene and privacy, acting as a significant constraint in promoting the accessibility of education for girls (Ministry of Education (2022)). A key driver of this lack of quality is that Liberia has, in recent years, operated at relatively low levels of educational expenditure as a percentage of GDP. This is shown in Figure 3, which compares Liberia's rate of education spending to that of its region and the world.

Figure 3: Education Spending as a Percentage of GDP from 2012-2021

This highlights the potential for a greater rate of investment into schooling to attempt to tackle the quality issues faced. Moreover, any policy introduced to increase attainment, including the promotion of remittance flows, should be met in tandem with an initiative to improve the quality of education provided. Only through a comprehensive approach that tackles both attainment and quality can Liberia expect to drive up the average level of human capital for its populous.

9. Conclusion

This paper utilises the 2014-2015 Liberian Household Income and Expenditure Survey to explore the impact of remittances on the educational attainment of Liberian individuals aged 6-24. Using both a standard and IV probit model, I discovered that both receiving remittances and the value of remittances received have a positive and significant marginal effect on youth enrolment rates. This outcome was ascertained whilst controlling for several covariates and heteroskedasticity using robust standard errors. Through conducting this study, I also found that other characteristics including gender and household wealth (proxied by car ownership and labour income) make a significant difference to enrolment probabilities.

My research contributes to the existing literature in many ways. Firstly, the outcome that remittances positively affect educational attainment aligns with most of the existing literature. This outcome is of particular importance because the existing literature is not unanimous. Hence, this study serves to add credibility to the literature that sides with the notion of a positive and significant relationship. The second way in which this study contributes is that it shines light on an area of the world that up to now has been widely overlooked in the existing literature. There have, up to now, been very few publications investigating Sub-Saharan Africa, and to my best knowledge, no papers that have especially focused on Liberia. Also, my results suggest evidence of diminishing returns of remittance value on educational attainment. This is likely because at high values of remittances, household income will be significantly large enough that there exists no restrictions for that household's children to be enrolled in education, and any remittances received after this point will have an insignificant effect on enrolment probability.

Furthermore, as Liberia is a nation that is still in post-conflict recovery, my findings and policy recommendations will be particularly important in assisting Liberia to rebuild, especially the education system which was so adversely affected during the country's civil wars (Ministry of Education, (2016)). This verdict

of my paper has policy implications that will be of particular importance to the newly appointed President of Liberia, Joseph Boakai, who has declared the need for improvements to be made to the education system. However, improved attainment should not be the sole focus of the new government. The current insufficiencies in the quality of the education system emphasise the importance of increased public spending to make schooling more effective in developing the level of human capital of Liberia's youth.

10. Limitations and Future Research

A limitation of the research conducted was the year of collection of the survey data. The 2014-2015 data was used as it was the most recent census in Liberia that included the relevant characteristics needed to complete this study. This paper acknowledges the potential for the decade-old data to no longer reflect the true situation in Liberia. Nevertheless, the economic and social climate has stayed relatively constant in Liberia in recent years, with no significant advancements to note which could potentially invalidate the data set. Thus, despite the acknowledged concern, this paper concludes that the main data used is still applicable and trustworthy in the context of determining the effect of remittances on educational attainment.

Another limitation of this study stems from the use of survey data, as it allows for the potential for the misrepresentation of variables, either intentionally or not. One key variable applicable to this is *remitt_value*, as the individuals surveyed may not remember exactly what the correct value of remittances received was in the previous year, or they may choose to misrepresent this figure for unknown reasons. If this occurs to a large enough extent, the results from the analysis conducted could be altered, and the validity of the conclusions called into question. Fully realising this potential issue, this study chose to incorporate two independent variables of interest for remittances, the other being a binary variable of remittance receipt, which will be simpler to remember. This decision acts to mitigate any concern of bias resulting from the misremembering of the true value of remittances. Ultimately, the results found for both independent variables were congruent and significant. Thus, this paper argues that the conclusion drawn that an increase in the value of remittances positively influences school enrolment is dependable and beyond scrutiny.

Finally, whilst my study does act to bridge an evident gap in the literature, there is still scope for further research. Relating directly to my paper, some of the findings were unexpected and will benefit from a more refined study. Specifically, the influence of father's education and the mother being alive both were negative, contrary to existing literature and rationality. Whilst these results do not limit the main focus of my research, it is important that these relationships are explored with a greater priority in future studies. Perhaps if a larger or more recent data set is made available in Liberia or a similar country, then more significant and informative results can be determined.

Even though there has been ample research made in this field at an aggregate level, there are still key factors that are yet to be explored with great depth. For example, what role does the age of the household head have on school enrolment possibilities, or how do remittances influence education attainment during or following directly from a conflict or natural disaster? Another area for potential research is investigating the effect of receiving remittances on educational outcomes, represented by test scores. A study focusing on this relationship would provide an interesting and unprecedented result that has not, as of now, been determined. A potential limiting factor to conducting this research could be the availability of data at a household level that is relevant to remittances and test scores. To complete this study, survey data will need to be collected on a large number of households, with questions pertaining to household characteristics, the level of remittances over recent years and the test scores of the household's children.

To summarise, even in light of its limitations and its potential for further study, this paper contributes significantly to the literature. My research is one of the first analyses in this region, and the results determined can act as the groundwork for future policy implementations or further study.

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